

CONCEPT OF MANAS: AN AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE**Dr. Bhagyashree R. Parvatikar*¹, Dr. Brijesh R. Mishra²**¹Post Graduate Scholar, Dept. of *Ayurveda Samhita and Siddhant*, Shri Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India.²Principal & HOD, Dept. of *Ayurveda Samhita and Siddhant*, Shri Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India.**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Bhagyashree R. Parvatikar*¹, Dr. Brijesh R. Mishra². (2026). CONCEPT OF MANAS: AN AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(1), 70-73.
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ABSTRACT

The term *Ayurveda* comes from Sanskrit words *Ayur* (life) and *veda* (Science). It emphasizes on prevention of the health of a healthy individual and treatment of diseased individual. It explains health is not only the absence of disease but a balanced state of body, mind and spirit. *Ayurveda*, the ancient Indian system of medicine, recognizes health as a balanced state of body (*Sharira*), mind (*Manas*), and soul (*Aatma*). The definition of *Ayu* in *Ayurveda*, states that *Ayu* is the conjugation of the Body, *Indriyas*, *Aatma* and *Sattva*. Among these, *Manas* plays a central role in governing perception, cognition, and behaviour. Classical *Ayurvedic* texts describe *Manas* as an internal organ (*Antahkarana*) responsible for receiving sensory information, processing cognition, regulating emotions and initiating voluntary actions. It acts as the interface between *Aatma* (Consciousness), *Indriyas* (sense organs), and *Sharira* (body). *Ayurveda* attributes mental functioning to the balanced interaction of three *Gunas* (qualities), *Sattva*, *Rajas* and *Tamas*, each contributes to psychological stability or disturbance. *Sattva* represents clarity and harmony. *Rajas* signifies activity and restlessness and *Tamas* reflects inertia and confusion. This article presents a scientific exploration of *Manas* from *Ayurvedic* perspectives, highlighting its Definition, structure, functions, location, qualities, unique properties, *Manas Doshas*, *Sattva sara Lakshanas* and relevance in psychosomatic health. The review also highlights classical descriptions of *Manovaha strotas*. The study highlights *Ayurveda*'s holistic approach to mental well being.

KEYWORDS: *Manas, Antahkarana, Aatma, Indriyas, Manovaha Strotas.***INTRODUCTION**

Over the years, scientists have been trying to explore evolutionary specialization of human brain and its one of the most outstanding features of high intelligence which really makes man different from other animals. This high intelligence is directly associated with excellent motor control, specified sensory functions and other higher mental activities which are linked with greatest neurological development.^[1] *Ayurveda*, the ancient Indian "Science of Life," views human existence as an interplay of physical, mental, and spiritual dimensions. The mind, or *Manas*, is an essential component of this triad and is crucial for perception, cognition, and volition. The definition of "Ayu" itself states the importance of *Sattva* i.e. *Ayu* is the conjugation of the body, *Indriyas*, *Atma* and *Sattva*. Among the nine *Karana Dravyas* it is described. "*Manas*" is described in various

forms in classics by *Acharya*'s as "*Amurtya dravya*" which has no structure but its activities are determined by its daily activities.^[3]

Manas is an *Ubhayatmaka Indriya* i.e. both *Jnanendriya* and *Karmendriya*. Also known as *Antarindriya* or *Antahkarana*. The source from which knowledge and thoughts arrive is called *Manas*. *Manas* is without any *Rupa*. It is *Nirvikara*. As it is an *Atindriya Swaroopa* could be understood through *Lakshanas*. *Manas* is exposed to *Vedanas* like *Sukha*, *Dukha*, *Vichara*, *Krodha*, *Kama* etc. only through *Manas*. *Charakacharya* has mentioned *Manas* in *Sharirasthan* along with functions of *Manas*. In *Vimanasthan* he has not mentioned *Manovaha Strotas* separately but in *Indriyasthan* and *Chikitsasthan* *Manovaha Strotas* is mentioned. *Manas* which is known as mind is very well described in *Ayurveda*.^[4] This paper

seeks to elucidate the *Ayurvedic* understanding of *Manas* and its relevance to contemporary mental-health science.

- **Vyutpatti (Etymology) of Manas**

The word “*Manah*” is derived from root “*Mana*” adding the suffix “*Asuna*”, with the following meanings:

- a) Which leads to knowledge (*Shabdakalpadruma*)
- b) Which analyses by special knowledge (*Maha Bharata*)^[2]

- **Lakshana Of Manas (Characteristics / Function)**

1. The faculty which controls, coordinates, and directs the senses is called the mind.^[5]
2. The characteristic of the mind is both the presence and absence of knowledge.^[6]

Even when the soul, senses, and their objects are in contact, knowledge does not arise without the participation of the mind.

- **Sthana Of Manas (Location of Mind)**

1. The mind is located in the heart (*hridaya*).^[7]
2. The mind is the substratum of mental faculties such as *sattva*, and it is the base for consciousness in the body.^[8]
3. According to *Bhela Samhita*, the mind resides in the head, beneath the palate, and governs all the senses.

- **Vishaya Of Manas (Objects of Mind)**

The objects of the mind are of five types^[9]:

1. **Chintya** – That which is thought upon as duty or non-duty.
2. **Vicharya** – That which is examined logically for validity or invalidity.
3. **Uhya** – That which is inferred or supposed, e.g., “This may happen like this.”
4. **Dhyeya** – That which is contemplated upon for realization.
5. **Sankalpya** – That which is determined as good or bad, desirable or undesirable.

Thus, everything that is known by the mind is called *artha* (object).

- **Functions of the Mind (Mano-Karma)**^[10]

1. **Control of the senses (Indriyabhigraha)**
 - The primary function of the mind is to regulate and direct the senses.
 - When the senses are inclined towards undesirable objects, it is the mind that restrains them.
 - The mind, being endowed with certain qualities, redirects the senses towards wholesome objects.

2. **Self-regulation (Svasya Nigraha)**

- Restraining one’s own impulses is another function of the mind.
- The mind itself, when distracted towards unfavourable objects, is brought under control by the same mind.

3. **Deliberation and Reflection (Uhya and Vicharya)**

- *Uhya* – supposition or assumption, mental construction.
- *Vicharya* – reasoning or discrimination, i.e., deciding whether something is acceptable or to be rejected.
- This process of deliberation eventually leads to the operation of *Buddhi* (intellect), which makes the final determination.

4. **The Chain of Cognitive Functions**

Indriya (senses): perceive objects without judgment.

Manas (mind): imagines and contemplates, weighing acceptability or rejection.

Ahamkara (ego): associates the perception with self – “this is mine, I am the agent here.”

Buddhi (intellect): makes the final decision – “I will abandon this (as faulty) and accept that (as virtuous).”

- **Qualities of the Mind (Mano-Guna)**^[11]

1. **Two natural qualities of the mind**

- **Anutva (minuteness)**

- The mind is subtle and minute.
- Since many senses are governed by the mind simultaneously, yet experiences do not arise all at once, it indicates that the mind is atomic and functions in a unitary manner.

- **Ekatva (oneness)**

- The mind can engage with only one sense organ at a time.
- Simultaneous multiple perceptions do not occur, hence its unity is established.

2. **Two acquired qualities (linked with Doshas)**

Rajas (agitation, activity) and *Tamas* (inertia, dullness):

- These two are considered defects of the mind as they disturb its natural clarity.
- Just as physical doshas cause diseases in the body, *Rajas* and *Tamas* cause disorders of the mind, leading to suffering.

- **Manasa Dosha (mental defects) and Dharaniya Vega (urges to be restrained)**^[12]

- The two mental *doshas* are *Rajas* and *Tamas*.

The disorders (*vikara*) caused by them include:

1. Desire (*Kama*),
2. Anger (*Krodha*),
3. Greed (*Lobha*),
4. Delusion (*Moha*),
5. Envy (*Irshya*),
6. Pride (*Mana*),
7. Arrogance (*Mada*),
8. Sorrow (*Shoka*),
9. Restlessness/Agitation (*Chittodvega*),
10. Fear (*Bhaya*),

11. Excessive Excitement (*Harṣha*) and others.
 - These are considered mental afflictions that disturb the balance of the mind.
 - Also mentioned as urges to be Restrained (*Dharaniya Vega*) according to *Charak Samhita*.^[13]

- **Importance of *Manas* examination in patients**

Manas examination is important in examination of patient, the physician should examine the patient with respect to the following ten factors^[14]:

1. *Prakṛuti* (natural constitution),
2. *Vikṛuti* (morbid state or pathology),
3. *Sara* (excellence of body tissues),
4. *Samhanana* (compactness of the body),
5. *Pramāṇa* (measurement or proportion of the body),
6. *Satmya* (suitability/adaptability to various substances),
7. *Sattva* (mental strength)
8. *Ahara-shakti* (capacity for intake and digestion of food),
9. *Vyayama-shakti* (capacity for exercise and physical activity),
10. *Vayah* (age).

These tenfold examinations are conducted for the proper assessment of strength and other qualities of the patient.

- **Classification Of *Sattva***

This (*sattva*, mental strength) is of three kinds according to its variation in power^[15]:

1. Superior (*Pravara*),
2. Medium (*Madhyama*), and
3. Inferior (*Avara*).

- ***Sattva Sara Lakshana* (Excellence of *sattva* / Mental strength)**

Those who are possessed of essence of *sattva* (*sattva-sara*) are characterized as^[16]:

1. Endowed with good memory,
2. Devotion and faith,
3. Gratitude,
4. Wisdom and intelligence,
5. Purity,
6. Great enthusiasm,
7. Skillfulness,
8. Courage,
9. Valor in battle,
10. Free from grief and depression,
11. Steady in gait,
12. Profound in intellect and actions,
13. Inclined towards auspicious pursuits.

- **Unity of the Mind (*Mano-Ekatva*)^[17]**

- Because of its involvement in self, sense objects, and thoughts, and its association with the three *gunas* (*sattva*, *rajas*, *tamas*), it may appear as if there are many minds within a single person.

- But in reality, the mind is only one – it cannot operate in multiple places at the same time.

- Therefore, there is no simultaneous functioning of all sense organs.

For example: when someone eats a long sugarcane stick, it seems as though five sense perceptions (taste, sight, touch, smell, sound) arise together. But this is an illusion – just like perceiving a hundred lotuses at once.

x- If knowledge truly arose simultaneously, then whenever there is contact with objects, all perceptions would always occur together. But this does not happen.

- Hence, the mind is not great or extensive in size, because if it were vast, it could coordinate all five senses at once. Since this is not possible, the mind must be minute and singular (*eka-anu-rupa*) in nature.

- **Suprasensory Nature of the Mind (*Mano-Atindriyatva*)^[18]**

- The mind is called *Atindriya* – “beyond the senses,” also referred to as *Chetas* or *Sattva*.

- Its activity depends upon the soul (*Atman*).

- The senses like eyes, ears, etc., function only in their specific domains (vision, sound, etc.), But the mind acts as the cause, support, and coordinator for all sensory knowledge.

- Thus, mind is considered a suprasensory faculty – not limited to a single sense organ but enabling and validating their functions.

- **Channels of the Mind (*Manovaha Strotas*)**

- When the channels of the mind (*Manovaha Strotas*) are vitiated by strong *doshas*, a person experiences terrifying dreams at night.^[19]

- Though the channels of the mind are not described separately, since the mind itself is called “consciousness pervading the entire body”^[20], it is understood that all bodily channels are included.

- However, specifically, because the mind is seated in the heart, the ten vessels (*dhamanis*) connected with the heart are especially described as *Manovaha Strotas* (mind-carrying channels)

CONCLUSION

➤ *Charaka Samhita* gives a very good description of *Manas Siddhanta* including its normal and abnormal states, but all these descriptions are highly scattered. Seeds of *Ayurvedic* concept of *Manas* are found in different philosophical texts, but *Ayurveda* considers it in an applied way.

➤ *Manas* is the connecting link between the *Aatma* with *Sharir* and hence influences both. *Manas* also play a role in keeping healthy status as well as in disease production.

➤ *Rajas* and *Tamas* are the two *Dosha* of *Manas* which play a major role in causing the diseases both psychological and somatic.^[4]

➤ *Manas Doshas* or *Dharaniya vegas* are urges that should be restrained.^[13]

➤ *Manas* examination is important in tenfold examination of patients.^[14]

➤ *Manas* is one and atomic (*Ekatva*, *Anutva*) – it cannot act simultaneously on multiple senses.^[17]

- *Manas* is suprasensory (*Atindriya*) – it coordinates and validates sensory knowledge, beyond the range of individual sense organs.^[18]
- *Manas* has its own channels (*Manovaha Strotas*) – mainly centered in the heart, disturbances in which cause abnormal perceptions and dreams.^[19]

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